

D8.10

Videos 1 project intro video + 1
new video per year to update
process + final conf video

PROJECT	BBTWINS
PROJECT NUMBER	101023334
PROJECT TITLE	Digital twins for the optimisation of agrifood value chain processes and the supply of quality biomass for bio-processing
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DELIVERABLE TITLE	Videos 1 project intro video + 1 new video per year to update process + final conf video
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LEAD BENEFICIARY NAME	REVOLVE
TYPE OF DELIVERABLE	DEMONSTRATOR
DISSEMINATION LEVEL	PUBLIC

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1. Overview of BBTWINS' videos

Deliverable D8.10 "Videos 1 project intro video + 1 new video per year to update process + final conf video" by REVOLVE MEDIA is a public demonstrator. It will include the following five videos:

1. The 'Project Intro Video' delivered in November 2021 (M6) – publicly available [via this link](#).
2. 'Project update video #1' to be delivered in November 2022 (M18)
3. 'Project update video #2' to be delivered in November 2023 (M30)
4. 'Project update video #3' to be delivered in November 2024 (M42)
5. 'Final conference video' to be delivered in May 2025 (M48) as part of the final conference.

These videos will be published via the REVOLVE YouTube Channel under the playlist 'BBTWINS | BBI JU Project'. From here the videos will also be shared via the project's social media channels, published on the project website and included in newsletters in order to maximise its impact. Additionally, hosting the videos on a familiar video player like YouTube increases the adaptability of the videos to different communication channels.

Being public deliverables, videos will be .mp4 format or similar. The size of a good quality 2-minute video in .mp4 is around 125 MB. Even if compressed to .zip or similar formats, videos are normally larger than the maximum size of 52 MB for a single file allowed by the SyGMA online tool for reporting deliverables. Consequently, in addition to publishing videos via the REVOLVE YouTube Channel, BBTWINS' videos will be formally reported in the form of a written report like the present one including a link to the corresponding, publicly available video.

2. Project Intro video

The project intro video has been designed as a general introduction to the project and the work that will be taking place over the next four years. The footage used introduces topics specific to the project – peach orchards and pig farms – while also showing more generic footage that places the project at the heart of the agri-food industry. This also presents the project’s work and future results as being applicable to the wider agri-food industry.

The video incorporates both free and paid footage, being efficient with our use of resources while also ensuring a high-quality video. We have also used footage taken by project partners, highlighting the work being done by the project and preventing the video from appearing too commercial.

REVOLVE has also developed a series of animations to highlight the digital aspects of the project and present the information in an accessible and digestible format.

Figure 1 - BBTWINS animation

The accessibility of the video is also reflected in its overall length – under two and a half minutes – highlighting the most important information but also holding the viewers attention.

Figure 2 - Peaches in a crate

The video also has an upbeat electronic soundtrack, representing the rhythm and purpose of the project while also keeping viewers engaged.

The video also includes all BBI JU and European Commission funding information, partner information and links to the project website and social media channels.

[The video can be viewed via the BBTWINS YouTube Playlist here.](#)